

GAI in Agile project

The purpose of this short survey is to investigate whether students in the course "Agile project" at Kristiania use artificial intelligence in their project. The answers will be used for research. All responses are anonymous.

By "artificial intelligence" in this context we refer more specifically to what is called generative artificial intelligence (GAI). Generative artificial intelligence is able to create new content or process existing content within

various forms of media. A common form of generative AI is language models (e.g. ChatGPT, Bing), but there are also variants that generate or process images (e.g. Midjourney, Stable Diffusion), audio (e.g. Musenet, Magenta) or video (eg DeepDream).

To what study program do you belong?

BIT - Programming

BIT - Interactive Design

BIT - Frontend- and mobile development

BIT - E-business

BA Cyber security

Not sure / Prefer not to answer

Have you been scrum master during this project?

No

Yes, at part of the project

Yes, during the whole project

What are your major responsibilities in the Agile project?

To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course?

Do not use

Rarely use

Use occasionally

Use often

What type of tasks do you personally use AI for in Agile project? Multiple answers

possible.

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «Rarely use eller Use occasionally eller Use often» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course?»

Generate/write text

Kvalitetssikre/redigere egen tekst (stavekontroll, omformulering, etc.)

Quality assurance/editing own text (spell check, reformulation, etc.)

Summarize existing text (articles, syllabus, own assignments, etc.)

Explain theme, syllabus, concepts, terminology, etc.

As a discussion partner, inspiration for tasks, brainstorming, etc.

Generating/writing code

Generate sound, image, or video

If you use AI in a way that is not captured by the options on the previous question, please explain here.

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «Rarely use eller Use occasionally eller Use often» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course?»

Why do you personally not use AI in the Agile project course?

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «Do not use» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course?»

To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course compared to other courses in your study program?

I use AI more often in Agile project than in other courses.

Approximately the same.

I use less AI in Agile project than in other courses.

Why do you use AI more often in Agile project than in other courses?

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «I use AI more often in Agile project than in other courses.» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course compared to other courses in your study program?»

Why do you use less AI in Agile project than in other courses?

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «I use less AI in Agile project than in other courses.» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you personally use artificial intelligence (AI) in the Agile project course compared to other courses in your study program?»

To what extent do you think AI will affect your everyday work in your future working career?

Will not affect my everyday work at all

To some degree

To a high degree

To a very high degree

To what extent do you think the use of AI should be included in the teaching of the Agile project course?

Does not require the use of AI at all.

To some degree

To a high degree

To a very high degree

Do you have any input on how AI can be used in teaching the Agile project course?

Dette elementet vises kun dersom alternativet «To some degree eller To a high degree eller To a very high degree» er valgt i spørsmålet «To what extent do you think the use of AI should be included in the teaching of the Agile project course?»

Have the use of AI in the project been discussed in your group? If so, can you tell us what you have discussed?

Are there any tasks in the Agile project where you are not allowed to use AI tools?

What are the main positive effects of using AI tools in the Agile project course?

What are the main negative effects of using AI tools within the development team in the Agile project course?

Have you experienced any challenges using AI tools in your group?

Finally: Do you have anything to add regarding using AI in a project?